

CHEMICAL STUDIES OF SOME INDIAN LAURACEAE FATS. PART I

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The chemical composition of the mixed fatty acids including unsaponifiable matter of the five Lauraceae fats have been studied by the modified method consisting of crystallisation of trilaurin of the fats from alcohol and of separation and identification of the individual fatty acids in the alcohol-soluble portion of the fats in the usual manner.

The glyceride composition of the Lauraceae fats has been arrived at by employing the two Kartha's methods for their estimation.

The seeds of the plants of Lauraceae family contain a large quantity of a fatty oil (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 1918, p. 1103). Puntambekar and Krishna (this *Journal*, 1933, 10, 395) investigated the fat obtained from *Actinodaphne hookeri* Meisn. in 48% yield and found it to consist of the glycerides of 96% lauric acid and 4% oleic acid. Isolation of the free trilaurin or lauric acid from the fat has been a very simple matter. Not many examples are known where a fat from a natural source has been found to consist mostly of a glyceride of a simple fatty acid, and therefore the investigation on the fats from other species of this family has been of further academic interest. It has also commercial interest as a source of excellent detergent, satisfactory lubricating agent for watches and other delicate machines and as a wetting agent for insecticidal preparations. An opportunity was therefore taken to study the component fatty acids and the glycerides of the following species of Lauraceae family: *Litsaea chinensis* Lamk, *Litsaea citrata* Blume, *Litsaea lanuginosa* Nees, *Litsaea zeylanica* Nees and *Actinodaphne angustifolia* Nees.

Besides the work of Puntambekar (this *Journal*, *Ind & News Ed.*, 1938, 1, 21) on the physico-chemical characteristics of the fats from the seeds of the above mentioned species, the only other work on them has been reported by Gunde and Hilditch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1610) and Kane (*Indian Soap J.*, 1951, 17, 52). The present investigation has been carried on the old samples of the fats, and so variations in acid and iodine values have been experienced due to their partial hydrolysis. In all cases the fats were from samples expressed from kernels and did not contain any pericarp oil.

EXPERIMENTAL

The physico-chemical characteristics of the fats obtained from the above mentioned samples have been determined by the commonly used methods and tabulated below.

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TABLE I

Physico-chemical characteristics of the Lauraceae fats.

	<i>L. chinensis.</i>	<i>L. citrata.</i>	<i>L. lanuginosa.</i>	<i>L. zeylanica.</i>	<i>Actinodaphne angustifolia.</i>
Colour ...	Pale yellow	Pale yellow	Light brown	Pale yellow	Pale yellow
M. P. ...	39-41°	40-42°	39-41°	35-36°	42-45°
Sp. gr. ...	0.915/40°	0.9118/35°	0.9234/35°	0.9230/30°	0.9209/40°
Ref. ind. at 40°	1.4451	1.4403	1.4452	1.4451	1.4403
Iodine value (Hanus) ...	4.45	5.6	9.72	15.1	7.1
Sapon. value	257.71	254.25	260.0	258.6	251.85
Ester value ...	220.5	196.35	191.4	171.66	225.95
Acid value ...	37.21	67.9	69.5	86.94	25.9
Hebner value(%)	91.9	88.7	88.1	82.35	86.2
Acetyl value ...	23.8	17.35	19.25	16.74	20.32
Unsap. matter (%)	1.25	1.7	1.3	1.3	1.25
Trilaurin crystallised out(%)	73.8	70.4	54.0	...	83.4

Composition of the Fats and their Fatty Acids.—The fats when crystallised from a large volume of alcohol were obtained in fine silky needles, m.p. 45-46°, sap. value, 264 and I. V. I. I. On saponification, they gave an acid which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 43-44° and had a mean M. W. of 200.5. The mixed melting point of this acid with an authentic sample of lauric acid remained unchanged. These facts indicated that the fats were mostly trilaurin.

Component Fatty Acids

For the determination of the composition of the fatty acids, as much as possible of the sparingly soluble trilaurin of iodine value 0.0 was removed by crystallisation of the fats from 95% alcohol and the residue (glycerides, soluble in alcohol) left in the mother-liquor was saponified and separated into 'solid acids' and 'liquid acids' by Twitchell's method modified by Hilditch ("The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", 1949, p. 468).

Liquid Acids.—A portion of the 'liquid acids' on bromination (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils and Fats", 1921, Vol I, p. 581) did not yield any of the hexabromides and tetrabromides, thus showing the absence of linolenic and linoleic acid respectively. Thus, only the possibility of formation of dibromide of the oleic acid remained and its presence was confirmed in the residual brominated product after removal of the petroleum ether by distillation under vacuum, as described below

TABLE II

Mixed fatty acids of the alcohol-soluble glycerides.

	<i>L. chinensis.</i>	<i>L. citrata.</i>	<i>L. lanuginosa.</i>	<i>L. zeylanica.</i>	<i>Actinodaphne angustifolia.</i>
Wt. of the fat taken(g.)	260.0	110.0	92.0	69.0	96.4
Wt. of the residual fat portion, soluble in alcohol, obtained (g.)	68.0	33.6	42.3	...	16.0
I. V. of the mixed fatty acids of the glycerides portion.	7.61	7.5	21.65	22.0	15.9
Mean M. W. of the mixed fatty acids of soluble glycerides portion.	206.0	208.0	215.0	211.0	213.0
I. V. of the solid acids.	3.48	4.14	6.63	6.0	6.07
Mean M. W. of the solid acids.	203.5	203.0	204.0	205.0	205.7
I. V. of the liquid acids.	29.95	21.3	34.4	34.0	20.6
Mean M. W. of the liquid acids.	217.7	218.0	225.0	221.0	222.8
% Solid acids.	60.1	66.7	45.2	60.7	49.6
% Liquid acids.	39.9	33.3	54.8	39.0	50.4

The brominated product was converted into the sodium soap by neutralising its alcoholic solution with dilute aqueous NaOH solution under constant stirring until a clear solution was formed. To this was added an aqueous solution of MgSO₄ with constant stirring to precipitate the magnesium soaps of dibromo-oleic as well as lauric acids and other lower saturated fatty acids that might be present. The magnesium soaps were filtered, washed, dried and dissolved in 50% hot ethanol in which the magnesium laurate and other lower saturated fatty acid salts easily dissolved (Lewkowitzsch, *ibid.*, p. 159), leaving behind magnesium dibromo-oleate which was again treated with 50% hot ethanol. This process was repeated 3 to 5 times to obtain a pure sample of the magnesium dibromo-oleate. The free dibromo-oleic acid was liberated from this product by heating it with an excess of mineral acid (dil. H₂SO₄). The upper layer of the separated fatty acid was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water to free it from the mineral acid and the ether was distilled off. The last traces of ether was removed under vacuum and the dibromo derivative of the oleic acid was dried by placing it overnight in a vacuum desiccator. The bromine content of dibromo-oleic acid (found: 36.76% ; calc. 36.18%) was determined by Stephanow's method (Coleman and Arnall, "Preparation and Analysis of Organic Chemistry", 1926, p. 287). All the alcoholic filtrates were combined and concentrated to a small volume on a water-bath to remove most of the ethanol. The residual magnesium soap was treated with H₂SO₄ (dil.) and the mixture was heated on a water-bath till a clear fatty layer was formed on the top. This was taken up in ether, washed free of the mineral

acids, dried over anhydrous $MgSO_4$ and the ether distilled off. The fatty acid on crystallisation from dilute acetone melted at $43-44^\circ$ and was identified as lauric acid by its mixed melting point with an authentic sample.

The presence of the oleic acid was further confirmed by the isolation of dihydroxystearic acid (m. p. $129-30^\circ$, mean M. W. 318.0) in the oxidised product of another portion of the liquid fatty acids by Lapworth and Mottram's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628).

Solid Acids.—The solid acids were converted into their methyl esters by treating with 5 times of methanol containing 3.5% HCl by the usual manner. The neutral methyl esters were fractionally distilled under reduced pressure with the following results. The acids were identified by subjecting them to recrystallisation from dilute ethanol and dilute acetone. These were confirmed as lauric acid by their melting point with an authentic sample. No other saturated acids could be detected. The following fractions were obtained in each case.

TABLE III

Name of the fat	Fr.	B.P.	S.E.	I.V.	Wt./g.	Methyl laurate.	Methyl oleate.
a. <i>L. chinensis</i> (29.2 g. of the methyl esters distilled at 9 mm.)	S ₁	120-125°	208.4	1.8	1.6158	1.6158 g.	...
	S ₂	125-132°	211.7	1.9	6.7337	6.7337	...
	S ₃	132-137°	213.5	1.8	11.9012	11.9012	...
	S ₄	137-142°	214.3	1.4	6.4884	6.4884	...
	S ₅	142-160°	217.1	2.0	1.0290	1.0062	0.0228 g.
	Residue	1.0413	1.0184	0.0229
	Loss	0.3906
Total	29.2000	28.7637	0.0457	
b. <i>L. citrata</i> (11.25 g. of the methyl esters distilled at 5 mm.)	S ₁	Up to 120°	211.0	1.5	1.673	1.673	...
	S ₂	120-124°	214.0	1.0	8.978	9.978	...
	Residue	0.486	0.486	...
	Loss	0.123
	Total	11.250	11.137	...
c. <i>L. lanuginosa</i> (13.0757 g. of the methyl esters distilled at 4 mm.)	S ₁	110-120°	213.0	1.1	3.073	3.073	...
	S ₂	120-125°	215.0	1.2	3.0287	3.0287	...
	S ₃	125-130°	225.5	20.1	6.0095	4.7845	1.225
	Residue	0.8293	0.6411	0.1882
	Loss	0.1352
Total	13.0757	11.5273	1.4132	
d. <i>L. zeylanica</i> (30.0 g. of the methyl esters distilled at 2 mm.)	S ₁	105-110°	218.0	1.5	1.9486	1.8426	0.106
	S ₂	110-115°	221.0	10.0	12.659	11.202	1.457
	S ₃	115-120°	222.0	10.5	13.8545	12.0554	1.7991
	Residue	1.3961	1.2320	0.1642
	Loss	0.1418
Total	30.00	26.332	3.5252	

e. *Actinodaphne angustifolia*: The amount of the solid acids obtained was insufficient to prepare their methyl esters and their subsequent fractional distillation purpose. The solid acids on crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave a product which was yellow in colour and on recrystallisation from dilute acetone yielded a product, m.p. $43-44^\circ$ and mean M.W. 200.1. This was identified as lauric acid.

Calculation of the Component Fatty Acids of Litsaea chinensis Seed Fat

An example is given below to show how the component fatty acids of a Lauraceae fat have been calculated :

1. Amount of the mixed fatty acids obtained from 68 g. of alcohol-soluble fat = 58.0 g.
2. Amount of 'solid acids' obtained by Twitchell's method from 55.0 g. of the mixed fatty acids = 33.0 g.
3. Amount of 'solid acids' present in 58.0 g. of the mixed fatty acids (1) = $\frac{33.0 \times 58.0}{55.0}$
= 34.79 g.
4. Amount of the 'liquid acids' obtained from 55.0 g. of the mixed fatty acids by Twitchell's method = 22.0 g.
5. The amount of 'liquid acids' present in 58.0 g. of the mixed fatty acids (1) = $\frac{22.0 \times 58.0}{55.0}$
= 23.21 g.
6. Amount of methyl laurate obtained by the fractional distillation of 29.2 g. of 'solid acids' esters = 28.76 g.
7. Equivalent quantity of lauric acid in (6) = 28.76×0.9345
= 26.87 g.
8. Amount of methyl oleate obtained from 29.2 g. of 'solid acids' esters = 0.0457 g.
9. Equivalent quantity of oleic acid (8) = 0.0457×0.9527
= 0.043 g.
10. Amount of the lauric acid present in 34.79 g. of 'solid acids' = $\frac{26.87 \times 34.79}{26.91}$
= 34.72 g.
11. Amount of oleic acid in 34.79 g. of 'solid acids' = 0.07 g.
12. Amount of oleic acid in 'liquid acids' (4) 22.0 g. of I. V. 20.85 = 5.18 g.
13. Amount of oleic in 23.21 g. of 'liquid acids' (5) = $\frac{5.18 \times 23.21}{22.0}$
= 5.464 g.
14. Amount of lauric acid in 'liquid acids' (5) = (23.21 - 5.464)
= 17.746 g.
15. Total lauric acid in mixed fatty acids (1) = 34.72 (in 'solid acids') + 17.746 (in 'liquid acids')
= 52.466 g.
16. Total oleic acid in mixed fatty acids (1) = 5.464 + 0.07
= 5.534 g.

17. Trilaurin obtained by crystallisation from 260.0 g. of fat	= 192.0 g.
18. Amount of lauric acid present in 192.0 g. of trilaurin	= $\frac{600 \times 192.0}{638}$
	= 180.4 g.
19. Total lauric acid in mixed fatty acids of the whole fat	= (180.4 + 52.466)
	= 232.866 g.
20. Total mixed fatty acids + U.S.M. 232.866 (lauric acid)	
+ 5.534 (oleic acid) + 3.0 U.S.M	= 241.4 g.
21. % Lauric acid in (20)	= 96.27
22. % Oleic acid in (20)	= 2.32
23. % Unsaponifiable matter	= 1.41

Components :

Lauric acid	= 96.27%
Oleic acid	= 2.32%
Unsaponifiable matter	= 1.41%

TABLE IV

Component fatty acids of the five Lauraceae fats.

	Lauric acid.	Oleic acid.	Unsap. matter.
<i>L. chinensis</i>	96.27%	2.32%	1.41%
<i>L. citrata</i>	96.06	2.15	1.79
<i>L. lanuginosa</i>	88.05	10.41	1.54
<i>L. zeylanica</i>	76.70	21.90	1.40
<i>A. angustifolia</i>	96.60	2.10	1.30

Unsaponifiable Matter.—The sterol content of the unsaponifiable matter was estimated in each case by the digitonin-addition method (Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.*, p. 607). The filtrate from the above operation was evaporated to dryness. The residue was found to be mainly consisted of waxes, hydrocarbons and other higher alcohols. The acetyl derivative of sterol was prepared, m. p. 119-20°, and confirmed as sitosterol which is commonly present in the vegetable oils and fats.

Component Glycerides

Two quantitative methods have been used for the estimation of the glycerides of the Lauraceae fats, namely, (a) oxidation of the neutral fat by acetone-acetic acid-permanganate method (Kartha, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, **12A**, 504), used in the case of *L. chinensis*, *L. lanuginosa* and *A. hookeri*, and (b) examination of the melting points of fats and their mixed fatty acids (Kartha, *ibid.*, 1954, **13A**, 72) used in the case of *L. chinensis*, *L. citrata*, *L. lanuginosa*, *L. zeylanica* and *A. angustifolia*.

TABLE V
[By method a]

	<i>L. chinensis.</i>	<i>L. lanuginosa.</i>	<i>A. hookeri.</i>
Wt. of the neutralised fat taken for oxidation (g)	13.198	12.26	10.648
Wt. of the GS ₃ * obtained (g.)	12.53	9.81	10.1
I.V. of the GS ₃ *	1.0	0.5	1.0
No precipitate formed in the carbonate extract.	Shown the	absence of	GS ₂ U.
Acidified the above carbonate soln. with dil. H ₂ SO ₄ , saturated with common salt and extracted with ether, and the ether distilled off.	No residue left, thus showed the absence of GSU ₂ .		
% GS ₃ (found)	96.0	80.0	95.0
% Triaurin (calc.)	94.9	79.4	93.9
% Oleodilaurin (calc.)	1.1	0.6	1.1
% Triolein (calc.)	2.7	18.7	3.1
Unsaponifiable matter	1.3	1.3	1.9

* Triglycerides of saturated fatty acids.

Examination of the M.P. of Fats and their Mixed Fatty Acids.—It has been shown by Kartha (*loc. cit.*) that GS₃ content of the natural fat is generally a function of the saturated acid content and their difference in m.p. of fats and their mixed fatty acids. All biological and other factors influencing the regulation of chance distribution in the natural fat find expression in the difference of m.p. between the fats and their mixed fatty acids. The results are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Tri-saturated glycerides content of Lauraceae fats according to the present method of D.m.p. value (method b).*

Lauraceae fats.	S% (mol.) Expt	GS ₃ Chance % (mol) graph.	Melting points. Fats Mixed fatty acids.		D.m.p value (approx).	GS ₃ content	GS ₃ % (mol.) Calc.
<i>Litsaea chinensis</i>	98.5	96.0	105°F	100°F	0	1.0	96.0
<i>Litsaea citrata</i>	98.2	95.0	107°	103°	0	1.0	95.0
<i>Litsaea lanuginosa</i>	90.4	75.0	105°	100°	0	1.0	75.0
<i>Litsaea zeylanica</i>	84.4	59.0	97°	93°	0	1.0	59.0
<i>Actinodaphne angustifolia</i>	98.4	95.0	113°	109°	0	1.0	95.0

* D.m.p. value of fat has been termed as depression of melting point of fat as compared to the chance distribution from the same component acids and mathematically may be termed as (4+m.p. of the mixed fatty acids - m.p. of fat)°F.

DISCUSSION

Physico-chemical Constants.—The samples of the fats used in the present investigation were old and had been in storage since 1938; therefore some variations in acid, iodine, saponification, Hehner and acetyl values have been recorded in each

case. This might be attributed to the possibility that these fats have become rancid due to long storage with the formation of some free fatty acids and water-soluble degradation products of the constituent glycerides. Thus, the higher acid value found in each case is due to the presence of free fatty acids. Similarly, the slightly lower iodine value is due to the little breakdown and disappearance of some of the oleic acid glycerides to form the degradation products having no unsaturation. The Hehner values, lower than the theoretical values, could be explained by the fact that some of the lauric acid passed out in the soluble form into washings during the liberation of free acids from the saponified fat. Similar effect with respect to this value was also experienced by Schroeder (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1905, 243, 628) and Puntambekar (*loc.cit.*) during the investigation of the seed fats of *Litsaea chinensis* and *Actinodaphne hookeri* respectively. The high acetyl value indicates the presence of free hydroxy groups in the glycerol part of the fats due to the partial hydrolysis of the glycerides brought about by the rancid conditions attained by long storage, thereby setting one or two hydroxyl groups of the glycerol radical free.

Method of Estimation of Component Fatty Acids of Fats.—Owing to the preponderance of a single fatty acid (lauric 95%) in the mixed acid and in order to be able to definitely characterise the small amount of unsaturated acid present in them, the method adopted in the case of the seed fats of *Litsaea chinensis*, *Litsaea citrata*, *Litsaea lanuginosa* and *Actinodaphne angustifolia* was to separate out the crystallisable trilaurin from the fats by crystallisation from 95% ethanol, then to concentrate any free fatty acids or glycerides of oleic acid in the alcohol-soluble residual fatty portion. The alcohol-soluble fatty portion is subsequently treated as a new fat and subjected to saponification, liberation of the mixed fatty acids by Twitchell's method, conversion of the 'solid acids' into methyl esters and their fractional distillation under reduced pressure to isolate individual acids and the identification of the unsaturated acid in liquid acids by oxidation and bromination methods. In this way, it became quite simple to identify the relatively large amount of oleic acid in the alcohol-soluble portion of the fat as compared to in the original sample.

Bromination.—The identification of the oleic acid in the presence of a large quantity of low-molecular weight saturated acid, *i.e.* lauric acid, has been satisfactorily brought about by the bromination of the liquid acids (3-5 g.) and the separation of lauric acid from the brominated product by the magnesium salt formation of the total acids and their repeated crystallisation from 50% hot ethanol to get a pure sample of magnesium dibromo-oleate. The free dibromo-oleic acid was liberated from the product by heating it with dilute sulphuric acid and finally the bromine content of dibromo-oleic acid was determined by Stephanow's method.

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